

Research Article

Formulation Development and Evaluation of Herbal Based Anti-Dandruff Shampoo Powder

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of an herbal anti-dandruff shampoo powder incorporating natural ingredients such as Rosemary, Methi, Hibiscus, Neem, Ashwagandha, Reetha, Amla, Cinnamon, Kalonji, and Rose powder. The herbal powders were individually weighed, size-reduced using a mortar and pestle, and mixed thoroughly to achieve a homogeneous fine powder, which was then sieved through a 100-mesh sieve. The physicochemical evaluation revealed that the pH of the formulation (5.75) is within the ideal range for scalp health. The shampoo powder exhibited good washability, average foaming capacity, and desirable solubility. General powder characteristics confirmed its excellent flow properties. The moisture content was 3.41%, ensuring stability and minimizing microbial contamination. The total ash value and acid-insoluble ash indicated minimal impurities. The sensory evaluation confirmed a brown-colored, fine, smooth-textured formulation with characteristic odor and taste. These findings suggest that the herbal shampoo powder possesses desirable physicochemical properties, cleansing efficiency, and scalp compatibility, making it a promising natural alternative for hair care.

INTRODUCTION

Dandruff is one of the most common scalp disorders, affecting a significant portion of the global population. It is primarily caused by the excessive proliferation of *Malassezia* species, a type of yeast that thrives on the scalp's natural oils [1]. Other contributing factors include poor scalp hygiene, excessive sebum secretion, dry skin, stress and environmental conditions. The symptoms of dandruff include white or yellowish

flakes, scalp itching, and irritation, which can negatively impact an individual's quality of life. Conventional anti-dandruff shampoos often contain chemical-based active ingredients such as zinc pyrithione, ketoconazole, and selenium sulfide. While these agents are effective in reducing dandruff, prolonged use may lead to scalp dryness, irritation, and even resistance to antifungal treatments [2,3]. In contrast, herbal-based formulations have gained popularity due to their natural, gentle, and holistic approach to hair

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and scalp care. The use of plant-based ingredients offers multiple benefits, such as antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and conditioning properties, without causing adverse effects [4]. Several herbal ingredients have been widely recognized for their role in promoting scalp health and preventing dandruff. Rosemary is known for its strong antifungal and anti-inflammatory properties, which help in reducing dandruff and improving scalp circulation. Methi (Fenugreek) acts as an excellent cleansing agent due to its rich saponin content, effectively removing dirt and excess oil from the scalp. Hibiscus is a natural conditioner that nourishes the hair, strengthens the roots, and prevents scalp dryness. Neem, widely used in Ayurveda, exhibits potent antibacterial and antifungal properties, making it highly effective in treating dandruff and other scalp infections. Ashwagandha is known to enhance blood circulation to the scalp, strengthening the hair follicles and reducing stress-related hair fall [5]. Reetha (Soapnut) is a natural foaming agent that helps cleanse the scalp without stripping away its natural oils. Amla is rich in vitamin C and antioxidants, promoting hair darkening and preventing premature graying. Cinnamon possesses anti-lice and antimicrobial properties, contributing to overall scalp health. Kalonji (Black seed) is valued for its ability to stimulate hair growth and reduce hair thinning. Rose extract provides a pleasant fragrance while also exhibiting mild antimicrobial properties, enhancing the overall sensory appeal of the shampoo formulation. The present study aims to develop and evaluate an herbal-based anti-dandruff shampoo powder utilizing these natural ingredients [6,7]. The formulation is expected to provide an effective alternative to synthetic

shampoos while maintaining scalp health and promoting hair growth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Rosemary, Methi, Hibiscus, Neem, Ashwagandha, Reetha, Amla, Cinnamon, Kalonji and Rose powder was procured from local market.

METHOD OF PREPARATION:

The preparation of the anti-dandruff shampoo powder was carried out using a systematic and standardized approach. All the required herbal ingredients, including Rosemary, Methi, Hibiscus, Neem, Ashwagandha, Reetha, Amla, Cinnamon, Kalonji and Rose powder, were procured in dry form to ensure stability and ease of processing. Each ingredient was accurately weighed using a digital balance according to the required formulation quantity (Table 1). If any ingredient was not already in powdered form, it was subjected to size reduction using a mortar and pestle to obtain a fine powder. Once all the ingredients were finely powdered, they were thoroughly mixed using a mixer to ensure uniform distribution and homogeneity. The blended mixture was then passed through Sieve No. 100 to achieve a uniform particle size and enhance the quality of the final product. After sieving, the powder was weighed again to determine the final yield. The prepared shampoo powder was then stored in an airtight container to prevent moisture absorption and maintain its stability. The entire process was conducted under controlled environmental conditions to minimize contamination [8,9].

Table 1: Formulation table of anti-dandruff shampoo powder

Ingredients	Quantity (%W/W)	Activity
Rosemary	10	Antidandruff
Methi	10	Cleansing Agent
Hibiscus	10	Conditioning Agent
Neem	5	Anti-bacterial
Ashwagandha	5	Scalp circulation & Nourishment

Reetha	20	Foaming
Amla	15	Hair darkening
Cinnamon	8	Anti-lice agent
Kalonji	15	Hair growth
Rose	2	Fragrance

EVALUATION PARAMETERS [10-17]:

Organoleptic evaluation: Colour, taste, smell and texture were all evaluated as part of the organoleptic evaluation process.

General powder characteristic:

Angle of repose:

The fixed funnel method was used to calculate the angle of repose. A vertically adjustable funnel was used to pour the mixture until the desired maximum cone height (h) was reached. The following formula was used to determine the angle of repose and measure the heap's radius (r):

$$\text{Angle of repose } (\theta) = \tan^{-1} \frac{h}{r}$$

The radius of the base pile is denoted by r, the height of the pile by h, and the angle of repose by θ .

Table 2: Angle of repose

Angle of repose (θ)	Type of flow
< 25	Excellent
25 - 30	Good
30 - 40	Passable
> 40	Very poor

Bulk density:

The precisely weighed powder was poured into a graduated cylinder to measure bulk density. The powder's weight (M) and bulk volume (Vb) were calculated. The following formula was used to get the bulk density:

$$\text{Bulk density (BD)} = \frac{\text{Weight of powder (M)}}{\text{Bulk volume (Vb)}}$$

Tapped density:

The 100 ml measuring cylinder was filled with the sample powder. After that a fixed number of taps (100) were applied to the cylinder. Record the final volume and by the following equation the tapped density was calculated.

$$\text{Tapped Density (TD)} = \frac{\text{Weight of powder (M)}}{\text{Tapped volume (Vt)}}$$

Hausner's ratio:

The Hausner's ratio is an index of ease of flow of powder. The Hausner's ratio less than 1.25 indicates good flow. It is calculated by the formula

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density}}{\text{Bulk Density}}$$

Table 3: Hausner's ratio

Hausner's ratio	Property
0.1 - 1.25	Free flowing
1.25 - 1.6	Cohesive powder

Carr's index:

One of the most crucial metrics for describing the characteristics of powders and granules is Carr's index. From the following equation it can be calculated and category of Carr's Index is shown in the table 4.

$$\text{Carr's Index (I)} = \frac{\text{Tapped density (TD)} - \text{Bulk density (BD)}}{\text{Tapped density (TD)}} * 100$$

Table 4: Carr's Index

% Compressibility Index	Properties
5-12	Free Flowing
12-19	Good
19-21	Fair
23-31	Poor
33-38	Very poor
> 40	Extremely poor

Physicochemical Evaluation:

pH: The pH of a 10% shampoo solution in distilled water was measured at room temperature (25°C). The solution was prepared by dissolving the shampoo powder in distilled water, ensuring complete dispersion. The pH measurement was carried out using a digital pH meter.

Washability: The washability of the shampoo formulations was evaluated by manually applying the prepared shampoo powder to the skin and assessing its ease of removal with water. The extent of washability was determined based on the time required for complete rinsing and the presence of any residual formulation on the skin. This evaluation was conducted under standard conditions to ensure consistency in results.

Solubility: It is referring to the ability of a substance to dissolve in a given solvent, typically expressed in terms of parts of solvent required to dissolve one gram of a solid or one milliliter of a liquid. When the solubility of a pharmacopeial substance is not precisely known, descriptive terms are used to indicate its approximate solubility range. These descriptive terms include very soluble, freely soluble, soluble, sparingly soluble, slightly soluble, very slightly soluble and practically insoluble, based on the amount of solvent required for dissolution [18,19].

Table 5: Solubility Classification

Descriptive Term	Relative Quantity of Solvent Required
Very Soluble	Less than 1 part
Freely Soluble	1 to 10 parts
Soluble	10 to 30 parts
Sparingly Soluble	30 to 100 parts
Slightly Soluble	100 to 1000 parts
Very Slightly Soluble	1000 to 10,000 parts
Practically Insoluble	More than 10,000 parts

Moisture Content: The moisture content of the herbal shampoo powder was determined using the

loss on drying (LOD) method. Precisely 10 g of the shampoo powder was weighed and placed in a hot air oven set at 105°C. The sample was dried for an initial period, followed by additional 30-minute intervals until a constant weight was achieved, indicating the complete removal of moisture. The moisture content of each sample was then calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Moisture Content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Initial Weight} - \text{Final Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

This method ensures accurate assessment of residual moisture, which is crucial for stability, microbial resistance and shelf life of the herbal shampoo powder.

Ash value: The ash value determination was carried out to estimate the total inorganic content present in the herbal shampoo powder. Approximately 2 g of the powdered formulation was placed on a pre-weighed silica crucible and initially incinerated at a low temperature. The heat was gradually increased until the sample was completely burned, reaching a red-hot state. The crucible was then allowed to cool in a desiccator and the remaining ash was weighed. The total ash content was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Total Ash (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash}}{\text{Initial Weight of Sample}} \times 100$$

Acid-Insoluble Ash Value: It is determined to assess the presence of silica, sand and other insoluble impurities in the herbal shampoo powder. The total ash obtained from the previous ash value test was boiled with 25 mL of dilute hydrochloric acid (HCl) for 5 minutes to dissolve acid-soluble materials. The insoluble residue was then collected in a Gooch crucible, washed thoroughly with hot water to remove any remaining acid, and then ignited in a muffle furnace until a constant weight was achieved. The crucible was allowed to cool in a desiccator and

the final weight was recorded. The acid-insoluble ash was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Acid Insoluble Ash (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of Acid Insoluble Ash}}{\text{Initial Weight of Sample}} \times 100$$

Foaming Capacity: The foaming capacity of the herbal shampoo powder was evaluated using a foam stability test. Precisely 2 g of the shampoo powder was dispersed in 50 mL of water in a graduated cylinder. The mixture was shaken vigorously for a fixed duration to generate foam. The foam height was recorded immediately and then at specific time intervals to assess foam stability. The foaming capacity was calculated by measuring the initial foam volume and its retention over time.

$$\text{Foaming Capacity} = \frac{\text{Foam Volume at Time (t)}}{\text{Initial Foam Volume}} \times 100$$

This test determines the cleansing efficiency and surfactant properties of the herbal shampoo powder, which are critical for its effectiveness in removing dirt and oil [20,21].

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Organoleptic Evaluation:

Table 6: Organoleptic Evaluation Results:

Parameters	Observations
Colour	Brown
Odour	Characteristic
Taste	Characteristic
Texture	Fine smooth

General Powder Characteristic:

The general powder characteristics of the herbal shampoo powder were evaluated to assess its flowability, density and compressibility, which are critical for formulation stability and ease of handling. The angle of repose was found to be 24.7°, indicating good flow properties. The bulk density and tapped density were recorded as 0.45 gm/mL and 0.52 gm/mL, respectively, demonstrating a slight increase upon tapping,

which suggests minimal particle rearrangement. The Hausner's ratio, calculated as 1.18, falls within the acceptable range, confirming good flowability. Similarly, the compressibility index was determined to be 8.61%, further indicating excellent powder flow properties with minimal compressibility. These results suggest that the herbal shampoo powder exhibits ideal physical characteristics for formulation, packaging and application, ensuring ease of use and consistent performance.

Table 7: General Powder Characteristics

Parameter	Results
Angle of Repose	24.7
Bulk Density	0.45 gm/mL
Tapped Density	0.52 gm/mL
Hausner's Ratio	1.18
Compressibility Index	8.61

Physicochemical Evaluation:

The physicochemical evaluation of the herbal shampoo powder was conducted to assess its pH, washability, foaming capacity, solubility, moisture content and ash values, which are essential parameters for determining its quality, effectiveness and stability. The pH of the 10% shampoo solution was found to be 5.75, which is close to the natural pH of the scalp and hair, ensuring mildness and minimal irritation. The shampoo was found to be easily washable, indicating good rinsability without leaving residue. The foaming capacity was reported as average, suggesting moderate surfactant action for effective cleansing. The formulation was soluble, ensuring proper dispersion in water. The moisture content was 3.41%, which is within the acceptable range, ensuring stability and prevention of microbial growth. The total ash value was 4.7%, representing the total inorganic content, while the acid-insoluble ash was 1.08%, indicating the presence of minimal earthy and siliceous impurities. These findings confirm that the herbal shampoo powder meets the required quality

standards, ensuring good cleansing efficiency, scalp compatibility, and formulation stability.

Table 8: Physicochemical Evaluation of Herbal Shampoo Powder

Sr. No.	Physicochemical Parameter	Result
1	pH	5.75
2	Washability	Easily Washable
3	Foaming Capacity	Average
4	Solubility	Soluble
5	Moisture Content (%)	3.41
6	Total Ash Value (%)	4.7
7	Acid Insoluble Ash (%)	1.08

CONCLUSION

The formulated herbal anti-dandruff shampoo powder demonstrated optimal physicochemical properties, good flow characteristics, and effective cleansing ability. The pH of 5.75 ensures scalp compatibility, while the moisture content (3.41%) and ash values confirm formulation stability and minimal contamination. The washability and foaming properties suggest ease of application and effective dirt removal. The organoleptic evaluation confirmed an appealing appearance, texture, and characteristic herbal odor. The results validate the potential of herbal ingredients in hair care formulations, providing an eco-friendly, chemical-free alternative to synthetic shampoos. Further studies, including microbial analysis and stability studies, can enhance its commercial viability and consumer acceptability.

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